

THE IMPORTANCE OF FAMILY, NEIGHBORHOOD AND EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN PROMOTING NATIONAL AND SPIRITUAL VALUES

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Abstract: In this article, the effective organization of further strengthening of the cooperation of the family, neighborhood and educational institutions in the promotion of national and spiritual values, which are considered one of the main systems of our society, will be the basis for improving people's worldview and attitude to life. The widespread promotion of these values throughout our nation should first of all start from the family.

Key words: value, community, solidarity, kindness, humanity, strong, family, education, national spirit, culture.

National and spiritual values are one of the main systems of the society, a factor of improvement of positive and moral qualities, elimination of negative vices that hinder the development of the state and nation. These values include not only the interaction and relations between people, customs, culture and other skills, but are also important in ensuring the unity of society and developing humanity. In addition to the unique historical heritage, art and literature of nations and peoples, their customs and ceremonies, moral qualities and cultural attitudes are included in the system of national and spiritual values. These values play an important role in the socialization of the individual, in preserving the identity of the nation and in

educating the young generation. In national and spiritual values, people's outlook and attitude to life, inner nature and lifestyle are expressed, and the nation's spiritual world, way of thinking, hopes, conscience and honor are reflected.

Therefore, one of the current topics is to educate the population of our country in the spirit of respect for our national and spiritual values, to form their spiritual potential at a high level. This process, of course, starts from the so-called family, the place of education. Already, one of our great ancestors, Abu Rayhan Beruni, wrote valuable thoughts on the spiritual and moral education of children in many works such as "On Beliefs and Religions", "Memorials from Past Generations", "India". Beruni connects the spiritual qualities of a person and spiritual concepts in general with the nature of a person. Human nature is considered a parent, and it is emphasized that it is formed in the family first. After all, the influence and example of parents is enormous in the upbringing of the young generation in the spirit of national and spiritual values. Therefore, it is necessary to properly educate the young generation in the family. First of all, it is important to create a healthy environment in the family, to take into account the national spirit and lifestyle, for parents to be role models for children in every way, to form a feeling of love for the Motherland in children's minds, and to inculcate national and spiritual values. Because national and spiritual values are a perfect example of material and spiritual processes that always invite people to kindness and mutual harmony, and have become an integral part of the way of life of our people from century to century.

The role of the neighborhood, along with the family, is incomparable in promoting the values that are an important factor of the past, present and future of our nation to our people. The neighborhood acts as a great spiritual propagandist relying on age-old customs, customs, traditions and values. The ideas of goodness

are instilled in people's minds through the personal example of older people, the advice of the elderly, and the solidarity of society. Mahalla is a social institution of Uzbeks that was formed historically, lives and works with a single goal, reflects the unique characteristics of the people's lifestyle, mentality, and social life. The neighborhood is a sacred place that safely transmits our national traditions, customs, moral and spiritual values from generation to generation. The neighborhood plays an incomparable role in the formation of national and spiritual values, kindness, solidarity, humanity, fighting for the honor of the country, and mutual assistance in the hearts of every person. In fact, the neighborhood serves as a social-political, cultural-educational and educational community that unites people. In addition, as our honorable president Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in one of his speeches, "Our neighborhoods, which are the symbol of our national identity, bring peace and harmony, mutual respect and solidarity to our beautiful and unique homeland." We are all proud that it has become a place. Great work is being done in recent years to increase the prestige of this office, which is a unique system of self-management, to expand its rights and powers, and to strengthen its material and technical base and human resources.

One of our important achievements today is when we achieved the priority of national and spiritual values in education. This means inculcating the rich historical, national, and spiritual heritage in the young generation and providing education based on the traditions formed over the centuries. Because as Abdulla Awlani said: "Education is a matter of life or death for us, or salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster."

Along with family and community, educational institutions are equally responsible for promoting national and spiritual values to the population of our

country. After all, the establishment of mutual cooperation makes it easier to achieve the intended goal. Islam Karimov, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, said: "As we aim to build a legal, democratic and just state, it is the main and priority to raise the spirituality of our people, which embodies the cultural and most sensitive feelings, deep philosophical, political and legal concepts. has become one of the tasks", - we are once again convinced that our goal is to bring up an independent, free, educated, in a word, well-rounded person. Through education, young people are given the knowledge, skills, and abilities accumulated in human experience. delivered. If a person does not illuminate his path with the light of knowledge, he will remain in the street of darkness and ignorance. The light of a person's heart is strengthened by knowledge and enlightenment. The value of humanity is created by science. In addition, as a result of teaching various subjects to young people in educational institutions, personal qualities, beliefs, views on national values are formed in the minds of young people. In particular, among many educational institutions, high-level, meaningful events dedicated to the promotion of national and spiritual values are being organized. Such campaigns, without a doubt, serve as a program for educating the young generation to be loyal to national and spiritual values. In fact, one of the important tasks facing the educational process today is the use of national and spiritual values and traditions in the education of a perfect personality. Rudaki is one of the great thinkers of Central Asian nations. Ferdowsi. Ibn Sina, Nizami, Omar Khayyam. Yusuf Khos Hajib, Jalaluddin Rumi, Fariduddin Attar, Jami, Navoi, Babur, Fuzuli, Mashrab. Referring to the works of Huvaiddo and other famous poets and scientists, emphasizing that their valuable thoughts on education, morals and advice are derived from the content of national values, and through them, they teach the young generation to spiritual and spiritual beauty. It is

necessary to make efforts to introduce the school of wisdom, which is created on the ground of exhorting life experiences. In our country, the education and upbringing of a mature person has been raised to the level of state policy.

After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev once claimed "Uzbekistan is always faithful to its traditions in the field of inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance, and never deviates from this path. Today, we believe in our multi-ethnic people, our youth, who are our hope and support, and we are reaching the goal. Thinking about the happiness and maturity of our dear children and grandchildren, we are setting great tasks in front of us, looking forward to the bright future of our country and people. I think it is appropriate to quote the sentences of a nation with a great intention - its work will be great, its life will be bright and its future will be prosperous. In the behavior of some young people, it is possible to observe situations that do not correspond to our national values. It is possible to observe cases of incompatibility between the actions of some young people who support the ideas of religious extremism and fanaticism and our national values. Many of our young people have formed the right attitude towards universal and national values. Today, the attempt to educate young people against national values is increasing in the world information arena. Such actions are aimed at raising young people in a spirit of respect for their people, homeland and national values, and they have hidden goals to awaken a tendency to more western values."

In the worldview of the young generation, national spirituality the purpose of strengthening values is not to teach them to live based on their own values, but to encourage them to learn these national, spiritual and universal values and to live taking into account that the specific development of the country depends on them.

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